

paper Chain

FINAL DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN
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New Market Niches For the Pulp and Paper Industry Waste based on Circular Economy Approaches

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ABBREVIATIONS

C&D	Communication & Dissemination
PPI	Pulp & Paper Industries
EU	European Union
WP	Work Package
DMP	Data Management Plan
IMC	Innovation Management Committee
ORD	Open Research Data
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
OA	Open Access
ERC	European Research Council

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0. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document constitutes the Final Data Management Plan (hereafter, DMP) of the paperChain project, aiming at serving as reference guide in the use, characterization, storage, management and dissemination of data generated by the project.

According to the requirements and principles of Open Science of the European Union funded projects, dissemination of the results and outcomes must be done during the whole life of the project. Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must, as soon as possible, 'disseminate' its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium).

PaperChain Consortium participates in the Pilot on Open Research Data in Horizon 2020, which aims to improve and maximise access to, and re-use of research data generated.

The participation in the Pilot is flexible in the sense that it does not mean that all research data needs to be open. Rather, projects can define certain datasets to remain closed via this Final Data Management Plan (DMP). Open Access to peer reviewed publications is mandatory for every Horizon 2020 funded project, as described in the Article 29 of the Grant Agreement of the paperChain project.

Related to the research data management; all the research data linked to the project will be stored and preserved in an online data repository, linked to the website of the paperChain project. Moreover, this Final Data Management Plan is detailing which datasets have been generated by the project and their dissemination level, including if they will be used internally for exploitation of results (confidential data) or made them public and accessible for verification and re-use, including the way they will be curated and preserved.

Green Open Access (self-archiving) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications will be granted according to H2020 rules. The published work or the final peer-reviewed manuscript that has been accepted for publication is made freely and openly accessible by the author, or a representative, in an online repository. Some publishers have requested that open access be granted only after an embargo period has elapsed.

The present deliverable constitutes the final version of the DMP, submitted at the end of the project (M51), having adapted to the real progress of the paperChain project.

This deliverable has been developed according to the Template and Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020 (Version 3.2, 21st of March 2017), attached as Annex 1.

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1. Introduction

This document constitutes the last and final version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the project paperChain, within the EU Horizon 2020 framework, under the grant agreement No. 730305. The DMP ensures the correct transfer of some of the most relevant information developed in the project. The restrictions established during the project have been considered and satisfied by both the dissemination plan and the exploitation plan, by pursuing the basic principle of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

The first version of the DMP is submitted in Month 10 – M10- (March 2018), within the deliverable D9.2 “Data Management Plan”. The present updated and final version, following the progress of the project, is submitted in M51 (August 2021). At this point, it is remarkable that not all types of data are available at the beginning of the project, so this final version includes the outcomes of the project, reflecting the influence by external factors during its progress.

This document is describing the data management life cycle for all types of collected, generated, and processed datasets of the project. The way datasets are opened, shared, curated, and preserved is also defined. The aim is to control and ensure the quality of project outcomes datasets and define how data will be managed from the perspective of external accessibility and long-term archiving once the project has concluded.

1.1 Relevance of a Data Management Plan

According to the General Definition of **Data Management Plan**:

“Data Management Plans (DMPs) are a key element of good data management. A DMP describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by a Horizon 2020 project. As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR), a DMP should include information on:

- the handling of research data during and after the end of the project
- what data will be collected, processed and/or generated
- which methodology and standards will be applied
- whether data will be shared/made open access and
- how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project).

A DMP is required for all projects participating in the extended ORD pilot, unless they opt out of the ORD pilot.”

1.2 Working structure of the paperChain project

PaperChain project includes the following work packages (WPs), being the last three packages transversal to the whole project:

- WP1. Ethics requirements
- WP2. Pulp and Paper industry waste streams valorisation scenario
- WP3. Design of the novel circular economy models for the Pilot Cases
- WP4. Pre industrial Scale demonstration of the circular value chain
- WP5. Real Scale Demonstration of the circular value chain
- WP6. Life Cycle Sustainability
- WP7. Enabling market uptake: Product certification and circular economy model guidelines
- WP8. Market analysis, exploitation and replicability of circular economy models
- WP9. Communication and dissemination plan
- WP10. Project Management

1,3 Resource allocation. Roles, responsibilities and DMP implementation within the project

The responsible partner for data management in paperChain project is Greenize. The role of Greenize at this point is to ensure that demo cases leaders and researchers are publishing their data in an appropriate way, according to the DMP. The responsible of the generated scientific and research data are the partners involved in demo cases and other transversal work packages. IPR management, including restrictions and protections within publications for further exploitation will be in charge of the Innovation Management Committee.

The generated datasets will be useful for different stakeholders, such as potential end-users, policy makers, researchers, academia, construction companies, pulp & paper industries, waste managers and other players. Any stakeholder can use datasets in different ways, such as re-using outcomes, life-cycle analysis, valorisation of wastes, creation of new business models, etc.

A Knowledge Management strategy has been established in the project to secure the exploitation opportunities of the partners' project results emerging during the course of the project and secured in the Consortium Agreement. The Knowledge Management Strategy is part of the public deliverable D8.3 "Exploitation plan" due month 40. As a starting point, in the proposal submitted to the EC, several preliminary expected exploitable results were listed, along with partners involved, exploitation strategy and IPR agreement. The Innovation Management Committee (IMC) (chaired by LGI) will perform and coordinate all activities related to Knowledge Management and Intelligence Protection. Innovation Management Committee will support the partners in dealing with IPR aspects about the preliminary list of outputs. Access Rights to Results will be agreed on in the Consortium Agreement according to the rules set in the Grant Agreement.

2. Open Access and Open Research Data Pilot: Publications and Data

Open access (OA) means **free access to information and unrestricted use of electronic resources for everyone**. Any kind of digital content can be OA, from texts and data to software, audio, video, and multi-media.

In the field of research and development projects, open access typically refers to the disclosure of the technical and scientific information developed in the projects. This data is usually shared in two main manners:

- Scientific Publications in journals through peer-reviewed research articles
- Scientific research data (raw data and/or underlying publication data)

The present document is based on the “Guidelines on the Implementation of Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Projects supported by the European Research Council under Horizon 2020” , that beneficiaries must follow as mandatory in H2020 funded projects.

“Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results”, according to the Article 29 of the Grant Agreement.

Next chart, provided by the Participant Portal, shows open access to scientific publication and research data in the wider context of dissemination and exploitation:

FIGURE 1: CONTEXT OF DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION

As mentioned in the guide: In the context of research funding, **open access requirements** do not imply an obligation to publish results. The decision to publish is entirely up to the grant beneficiaries and the exploitation strategy of the project and consortium. Open access becomes an issue only if publication is chosen as a mean of dissemination.

Moreover, open access does **not affect the decision to exploit research results commercially**, e.g. through patenting. The decision on whether to publish through open access must come after the more general decision on whether to publish directly or to first seek protection. Furthermore, open access publications follows the same peer review process as non-open access ones.

2.1 Benefits of open access

The **benefits of publishing outcomes in open access** are many and varied. On one hand, it enhances the dissemination of projects and the links between the scientific community, fostering collaboration and avoiding duplication of efforts in the different subjects under study. As it is based on real research results, this exchange of information is essential to be more efficient in applied research.

On the other hand, it guarantees and democratizes access to information for society, the scientific community and other interested parties, such as innovative SMEs, for instance.

The latter undoubtedly improves the transparency of EU public research funding, improving its impact on the entire economic and social context.

2.2 Open access to scientific publications

The open access to publications mandate comprises 3 steps:

1. Depositing publications in repositories (online archive)
2. Selecting the open access route (green or gold open access)
3. Providing open access to publications

2.2.1 Step 1 – Depositing publications in repositories

Beneficiaries are required to deposit an electronic copy of the publication in a suitable repository. Publications must be "machine-readable", that is in a format that can be used and understood by a computer. They must therefore be stored in text file formats that are either standardized or otherwise publicly known so that anyone can develop new tools for working with the documents. Thus, scanned versions of printed publications do not fulfil this requirement.

Depositing is mandatory regardless of the open access mode selected. It must be done as soon as possible and at the latest upon publication. The beneficiary must also aim to deposit at the same time as the publication the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications ('underlying data'), ideally in a data repository. This is strongly encouraged but not mandatory. Beneficiaries are also invited to grant open access to this data, but they are not obliged to do so. The European Research Council (ERC) strongly encourages ERC funded researchers to use discipline-specific repositories for their publications.

2.2.2 Step 2: Green open access and Gold open access

Beneficiaries select one of the two main routes towards open access to publications, both equally valid:

1. Green open access (self-archiving): The published work or the final peer-reviewed manuscript that has been accepted for publication is made freely and openly accessible by the author, or a representative, in an online repository. Some publishers request that open access be granted only after an embargo period has elapsed.

2. Gold open access (open access publishing): The published work is made available in open access mode by the publisher immediately upon publication. The most common business model is based on one-off payments by authors (commonly called APCs – article processing charges – or BPCs – book processing charges). The costs of gold open access publications are eligible costs that can be charged against ERC grants, provided the costs are incurred during the duration of the project.

2.2.3 Step 3: Providing open access to deposited publications

Beneficiaries must ensure open access to the deposited version of their publications via the chosen repository. Open access should be provided as soon as possible and, in any case, no later than six months after the official publication date.

To be able to easily find the deposited publication, beneficiaries must also ensure open access – via the repository – to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication. This metadata must include a persistent identifier (such as the Digital Object Identifier, DOI) in order to allow easy and persistent referencing.

The European Commission encourages authors to retain their copyright and grant adequate licenses to publishers. [Creative Commons](#) offers useful licensing solutions (e.g. [CC BY](#)). This type of license is a good legal tool for providing open access in its broadest sense.

As mentioned, each beneficiary must ensure **open access** to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results, according to Horizon 2020 Regulation and the Rules of Participation Guide. This is implemented through the Article 29 of paperChain Grant Agreement. In particular, it must:

(a) as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications.

Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.

(b) ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the late

(i) on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or

(ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.

(c) ensure open access to the bibliographic metadata — via the repository — that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

2.3 Open access to research data

As it is mentioned in the Annex 1:

In Horizon 2020 the European Commission has been encouraging open access to and reuse of digital research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects through the Open Research Data Pilot (ORD Pilot), following FAIR data principles - all research data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). Examples of research data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images.

Under the pilot, open access should be provided to the data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications. Other data is also covered as specified in the data management plan.

The legal requirements for projects participating in this ORD Pilot are set out in Article 29.3 of the Grant Agreement: the beneficiary must deposit the data in a research data repository so that it is possible to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate the data, free of charge for any user. For ERC Work Programme 2016 projects, Article 29.3 will be only included in the Grant Agreement if the beneficiary has opted-in the ORD Pilot. Starting from ERC Work Programme 2017 projects, Article 29.3 will be included in the Grant Agreement as the default .

After the project has started, beneficiaries of the ERC projects participating in the ORD Pilot have to formulate a **Data Management Plan (DMP)**, a brief plan to define what data sets the project will generate or process, whether and how these data will be made accessible, and how they will be curated, stored and preserved. The DMP should also provide information on the measures taken to safeguard and protect sensitive data.

For ERC projects, the data management plan must address following issues:

1. Making data Findable
2. Making data openly Accessible
3. Making data Interoperable,
4. Increase data Re-use,
5. Allocation of recourses and data security

The data management plan will also have to specify if certain datasets remain closed and the reasons for not giving access should be given (for instance, if one of the project objectives would be jeopardised by providing open access to certain data or some of the generated data are considered sensitive, etc.).

Regarding the digital research data generated in the action ('data'), the beneficiaries must:

(a) deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user — the following:

(i) the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications as soon as possible;

(ii) other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the 'data management plan' (see Annex 1);

(b) provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves).

As an exception, the beneficiaries do not have to ensure open access to specific parts of their research data if the achievement of the action's main objective, as described in Annex 1, would be jeopardised by making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible. In this case, the data management plan must contain the reasons for not giving access.

2.4 Steps to participate in the ORD Pilot

Participants of the Open Research Data Pilot need to take the following three steps:

1. Deposit research data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, including associated metadata, in the repository as soon as possible. Also other data (for instance data not directly attributable to a publication, or raw data), including associated metadata, should be deposited – that is, according to the individual judgement by each project, specified in the data management plan.
2. Take measures to enable third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) this research data, for instance by attaching a [Creative Commons Attribution Licence \(CC BY\)](#) to the data deposited, or by waiving all interests associated to copyright and database protection using the CC0 tool. The [EUDAT B2SHARE tool](#) includes a built-in license wizard that facilitates the selection of an adequate license for research data.
3. Provide information via the chosen repository about the tools available in order for the beneficiaries to validate the results, e.g. specialised software or software code, algorithms and analysis protocols. Where possible, these tools or instruments should be provided.

3. FAIR data

The present document helps Horizon 2020 beneficiaries make their research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), to ensure it is soundly managed.

3. 1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data Management plan describes the way that each scientific and technical data generated by the PAPERCHAIN project will be named, sorted, shared, stored and disseminated during the whole life of the project. Other kind of data, such as deliverables or published papers of the project are directly excluded from the scope of the DMP and

included in deliverable 10.1 “Project management”; 10.2 “Quality Plan” and in the 9.1 “Communication & Dissemination Plan”.

Metadata are structured information that describes, explains, locates, and facilitates the context to make it findable and accessible by humans and machines. Metadata shall be considered as the formal means by which data is defined and by which the meaning of information is established.

Every dataset generated within the project will be fulfil with the appropriate metadata.

There are three types of metadata relevant to the subject presented in this document:

1. Descriptive metadata relative to the document such as Title, Author, Summary or Abstract
2. Hyper-textual or structural metadata, such as links or relationship between documents or collections
3. Administrative metadata such as archiving date or version number

Likewise, all bibliographic metadata generated by the project will include:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

The standard metadata that PAPERCHAIN project will subscribe to describe the dataset will be CERIF.

CERIF, Common European Research Information Format, is the recommended metadata standard for EU publications. More information about the **CERIF specification** and the overall integration with the **openAIRE** platform can be found within the following links:

<https://eurocris.org/news/cerif-rdf-mapped-most-common-metadata-schemes>

<https://zenodo.org/record/2316420#.YeVcvliZP0o>

Standardization of Data: Naming Conventions

The relevance of standardization of data is due to the diversify and huge amount of data which will be developed during the whole life of the project by the Consortium.

These datasets must be reachable by Consortium partners and accessible from outsiders. In order to make all datasets more accessible, they will be named in the same way according to the content developed and the responsible of them:

<i>pro</i>	<i>task</i>	<i>info</i>	<i>date</i>	<i>version</i>
pCh_	<i>T9.2_</i>	<i>Data Management_</i>	<i>20180306_</i>	<i>v03</i>

TABLE 1: NAMING CONVENTIONS

pCh_T9.2_Data Management_20180306_v03

- **pCh or paperChain:** refers to the short acronym or the complete naming of the paperChain Project
- **T9.2:** refers to the task which the data set is generated (or deliverable)
- **Data Management Plan:** refers to the information inside the file (no more than 15 characters)
- **20180306:** refers to date in the format YYYYMMDD
- **v03:** refers to the version of the file. Every different date will start again from v01

Search Keywords

Keywords summarize ideas and define what the topic is about. Keywords are crucial to establish a relationship between what the reader expect to find in their search and what it is delivered within the content submitted in the same search query.

In order to fulfil the need of well-established and relevant keywords, a two-factor methodology has been established for any delivered document.

Authors are the one that master the content that they wrote so, they will be prompted to introduce their own keywords for every paper delivered.

Once the content is ready, and the main keywords are defined, an automated scan will query for the most relevant, and most used words counted from the document.

The filtered result will be added as keyword to the main keyword list, a second filtering will be performed in order to avoid duplicities or irrelevant additions.

3.2. Making data openly accessible

ZENODO (an OpenAIRE and CERN collaboration) has been selected as main data repository for the paperChain project. ZENODO allows researchers to deposit both publications and data, while providing tools to link them. (Zenodo- PaperChain project - H2020 No 730305 -)

<https://zenodo.org/communities/h2020-paperchain-project/?page=1&size=20>

Partners in charge of each publication will be the responsible of repository selection.

3.3. Making data interoperable

Standard vocabulary and methodologies may be used on a case-by-case basis to make the data interoperable between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc.

- A list of acronyms and/or abbreviations will be provided at the beginning of every report
- Standard definitions such as waste, circular models etc. will be adopted and re-defined at the beginning of each report.

3.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

Data will be licensed under a well-known and world-wide adopted license, Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. This license provides freedom to use, share and adapt content, even commercially, as long as appropriate credit would be provided to the author.

This license is the most open license offered in Creative Commons ecosystem and is the most recommended for maximum dissemination and use of licensed materials.

More details in a legal form can be found within the following link:

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>

4. GDPR Compliance

The Data Management Plan is in line with the norms of the EU and Commission (according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) – REGULATION (EU) 2016/679), promoting best practice in Data Management. This regulation came into force on 25th May 2018.

The responsibility of protection and use of personal data is on the project partner which is collecting data. Questionnaire answers are anonymized, without possibility to connect with the individual person they belong to.

For the elaboration of this plan the following "[Rules for the protection of personal data inside and outside the EU](#)" have been followed

Personal data collected during the project were used only by project partners and only for necessities implementations in the project. The partner holding the data have to consider whether those data are needed for the implementation of the project. Personal data provided and held by partners shall not be distributed further within or outside the project.

The personal data collected within paperChain project are in electronic format, mainly in Microsoft Excel files, in order to made them machine-readable in case of internal transfer.

5. Datasets in paperChain

The paperChain webpage, www.paperchain.eu, is the core of all public dissemination activities and publications of the project, linking to open access repositories and social media platforms. The project is not re-using existing data but generating new datasets.

During the project, a set of deliverables have been developed in each of the work packages that make up the project. Some of these deliverables are confidential, but most of them are public. The responsible for defining and describing the content of each deliverable lies with the leader of each work package. In any case, these deliverables are available for viewing and downloading through the paperChain website, as well as in an open access repository such as Zenodo. This dataset corresponds to image file formats, such as PDF. This dataset corresponds to image file formats, such as PDF.

In parallel to the deliverables, communication and dissemination materials have been developed, aimed at wider audiences, policy makers, end-users and other stakeholders identified and described in the project. These materials are perfectly complementary to the rest of the publications and deliverables and their content is synthesised and designed to explain the complexity of each one of the pilots in a simple and friendly way and designed for non-specialised audiences that do not have much time or knowledge to deal with more technical options. They are also designed to capture the attention of potential end users and policy makers of the exploitation and replicability of the outcomes obtained from the project, presenting in a concise and friendly way the main results from the point of view of the adoption of the new circular economy models developed.

The communication materials developed are videos, posters, leaflets, brochures, banners published generically for the project and its pilots. In addition to this, there are also the

images that follow the implementation of the different pilots. They have multiple formats, corresponding to image, video, text, etc. files. They are collected, stored and preserved in different channels, depending on the target audience and adapted to the medium in which they are considered to have the greatest impact. Thus, the animation videos of the pilots and the project are available on the Youtube channel of paperChain (while the project has lasted) and of Greenize, the communication leader, once the project is over. The more technical posters are collected in the publications section of the paperChain website, as well as in an open access repository such as Zenodo.

Another set of data and information corresponds to the content and recordings for events and congresses, in person or digitally, which have been recorded and which constitute a valuable legacy in terms of dissemination of results, in many cases including a very interesting parallel debate with key actors. These types of communication materials specifically designed for events and conferences have been treated in the same way as those developed for the project in general. Thus, the videos have been preserved on Youtube, on the Youtube channel of paperChain (during the project) and of Greenize, the communication leader, after the end of the project. Posters and other presentations have been collected and stored in an open access repository such as Zenodo and made available on the paperChain website.

Another type of information and dataset generated corresponds to the publications on the project's social networks and the press releases sent to the media on important milestones of the project. This type of social media is a repository, storing the communications developed to tell the progress of the project and the implementation of the different pilots.

This DMP includes a list of all these communication and dissemination materials and deliverables but focuses on the rest of the data generated in the research activities of the project, both research data and technical publications and their corresponding metadata, as defined in the previous points. This last set of data, specific to the research, development and innovation sector, corresponds to the highest level of scientific-technical dissemination of the project and must be collected, stored and preserved correctly and managed through this DMP.

All these datasets are complementary and form a whole for information, communication and dissemination of the main advances and results of the project to the different stakeholders.

5.1 Dataset reference, name and description

To be able to distinguish and easily identify data sets from one another, they will be assigned with a unique name and have been listed in the section "PaperChain – REPOSITORY". Each data set that has been collected, processed or generated within the project and are accompanied by a brief description, adapting the template below:

Resource Name	Complete title of the resource
Resource Type	Choose one of the following values: Technical, Lexical/conceptual resource, corpus, language description
Media Type	The physical medium of the content representation, e.g., video, image, text, numerical data, n-grams, etc.
Language(s)	The language(s) of the resource content
License	The licensing terms and conditions under which the resource can be used
Distribution Medium	The medium, i.e., the channel used for delivery or providing access to the resource, e.g., accessible through interface, downloadable, CD/DVD, hard copy etc.
Usage	Foreseen use of the resource for which it has been produced
Size	Size of the resource with regard to a specific size unit measurement in form of a number
Description	A brief description of the main features of the resource (including url, if any)
Ownership of Data	Specify ownership of data : in our case, paperChain consortium most probably

A dataset is defined as a structured collection of information in a specific format. Often, a dataset is related through the contents of a matrix, where each column represents a variable and each row details each of the members that make up the dataset in question. The dataset may include information from one or more fields. Within the paperChain project, this dataset has been listed as it appears in the section "PaperChain-REPOSITORY".

5.2 Metadata

The most concrete definition of metadata is that it is "data about data" and serves to provide information about the data produced. Metadata consists of information that characterises data, describes the content, quality, condition, history, availability and other characteristics of the data. This "structured information describes, explains, locates and facilitates the means to make it easier to retrieve, use or manage an information resource".

Metadata has been already described above, on the FAIR section.

5.2 Data sharing

Throughout the project a specific web-based consortium platform was designed and created to facilitate the exchange of information between the members of the project. Within this webpage, it was structured including a continuous battery of resources, tools and files available to all members. All the deliverables presented, all the minutes of the meetings and the presentations made during the different general assemblies that have taken place were shared. In addition, it included a series of very useful resources for the development of the different paperChain tasks and deliverables. The platform was based on Google Drive and all documents were shared from the official paperChain account. The information hosted therefore had several levels of underlying security.

FIGURE 2 - SCREENSHOT OF CONSORTIUM PLATFORM WEBPAGE

The data and deliverables shared and submitted by the project partners has been classified from the beginning in 3 different dissemination levels, including their acronyms:

- PU: Public
- RE: Restricted to a specified working group
- CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (and commission services)

All material classified as PUBLIC dissemination is deemed uncontrolled.

Greenize, as partner responsible for this DMP along with all work package leaders, has coordinated together with the authors how data will be shared and more specifically the access procedures, the embargo periods – if needed-, the necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use, for all datasets that has been collected, generated, or processed in the project. In case the dataset cannot be shared, the reasons for this will be mentioned

(e.g., ethical, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial, privacy-related, security-related).

All deliverables have been shared directly from an open access repository, such as Zenodo, directly from the paperChain website or from other relevant platforms and social media repositories (such as twitter, slideshare, linkedin, Youtube). In the section "PaperChain-REPOSITORY" a detailed list is provided for each data.

For scientific publications, data has been shared only if all co-authors agree and if there is no embargo period for a specific journal. The lead author is responsible for getting approvals from the rest ones and for sharing the data and metadata on MPDI, Zenodo (www.zenodo.org), a widely accepted repository for research data. In some cases other open access repositories have been used by partners, anyway listed in the correspond section below. The lead author is also supposed to create an entry on OpenAIRE, a service that implements the Horizon 2020 Open Access mandate for publications and its Open research Data Pilot and may be used to reference both the publication and the data.

5.2 Data archiving and preservation

PaperChain webpage will be available for at least 2 years after the end of the project. Deliverables, research data and publications within the webpage are linking other repositories such as Zenodo, Open AIRE or MDPI. These tailored services aim to provide a long-term preservation of research data, keeping dataset under FAIR principles.

In parallel, the rest of communication and dissemination materials (videos, social media posts, images, etc.) have been uploaded to social media providers such as Youtube or Google Photos.

At the official project closure, all the data generated in the project will be transferred to a digital archive (coordinator responsibility), preserving all the data and metadata underlying and codified within the file naming convention already defined. This process will be done before 10 weeks after the formal closure of the project.

Archiving will create unique file identifiers, including metadata parameters for each data type. The metadata index structure will be used as inventory record of the extracted files and validated by the WP leader.

5.3 Data security

Data security has been a core concern during (and beyond) the whole life of the project. Several layers of security were established to prevent data loss, including data recovery tools. A dedicated cloud drive was configured to store all data, apart from local storage hard disks. This drive will be accessible only by the members with the appropriate privileges. This cloud drive was synchronized with the private platform in such a way that any member of the consortium can download the synchronized document without the need to access the main drive. This led to a more controlled environment with few administrators without losing the flexibility needed by other members.

The webpage is being continuously updated and maintained in order to prevent loss of information, attacks from hackers or falls.

6. Ethical aspects

PaperChain project will not collect personal data for its datasets. There are no ethical or legal issues having impact on data sharing in this project.

All ethical aspects related to the management of personal data compilation and protection has been considered in deliverables

1.1 "Ethics Requirements. Requirement number 1. Informed Consent Procedures" and

1.2 "Ethics requirements. Requirement number 2. Data management".

7. Conclusions

This deliverable contains the last and final release of the PaperChain Data Management Plan, aiming at serving as reference guide in the use, characterization, storage, management, and dissemination of data generated by the project. This deliverable should be read in association with all the referenced documents and the Consortium Agreement and with the annexes and guidelines proposed.

8. References (Bibliography)

-Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020, Version 3.2, 21 March 2017:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

-Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020, Version 2.1 15 February 2016:

https://www.cuni.cz/UK-5624-version1-h2020_hi_oa_data_mgt_en.pdf

-Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020, Version 3.0 26 July 2016:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

-Webpage of European Commission regarding Open Access:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/science-society/open_access

9. PaperChain – Repository

At month 51 of the project, the list with the dataset description, sharing, archiving, responsible and preservation is listed below:

9.1 ARTICLES IN NON INDEXED JOURNALS

#	YEAR	MONTH	ARTICLES IN NON INDEXED JOURNALS	MEDIA JOURNAL MAGAZINE	PARTNER INVOLVED	LINK to THE MEDIA
1	2019	January	Proyecto paperChain: Nuevos modelos de economía circular para la industria papelera Moisés Menendez, Antonio Cañas (Greenize), Juanjo Cepriá (Acciona)	FuturEnviro	GREENIZE, ACCIONA	https://futurenviro.es/paper-chain-project-new-circular-economy-models-for-the-paper-industry/
2	2019	March	Generacion de modelos de economía circular y uso de materiales de origen renovable para una construcción de firmes más sostenible. Carlos Martín Portugués, Raquel Casado Barrasa, Edith Guedella Bustamante (ACCIONA CONSTRUCCION)	"Carreteras" by Asociación Española de la Carretera	ACCIONA	https://www.aecarretera.com/servicios/publicaciones/revista-carreteras/articulos-publicados
3	2019	December	Cepriá, J. J., Orejana Gonzalez, R., de la Vega, Z., Martínez Reguero, A. H., Miró Recasens, J. R., Barra Bizinotto, M., ... & Baloochi, H. (2019). Cenizas volantes de papelera aplicadas a la construcción de carreteras: experiencias a gran escala del proyecto PaperChain. RETEMA Revista Técnica del Medio Ambiente, 219, 84-89.	PDF del nº 219 de RETEMA - Noviembre/Diciembre 2019	UPC, ACCIONA, SAICA	https://www.retema.es/revistas/noviembre-diciembre-b01qJ

9.2 ARTICLES IN INDEXED JOURNALS

#	PUBLIC ATION DATE	ARTICLES IN INDEXED JOURNALS	PARTNERS INVOLVED	WP	TOPICS	ACCESS RIGHT	REPOSITOR Y	DOI	JOURNAL TITLE
1	2020	Anna Virolainen; Christian Maurice and Thomas Pabst. (2019). Effective Oxygen Diffusion Coefficient of Till and Green Liquor Dregs (GLD) Mixes Used in Sealing Layer in Mine Waste Covers. Water Air Soil Pollut (2020) 231: 60.	LTU	WP5	Efficiency and stability of the sealing layer	Open Access	SPRINGER	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-020-4431-3	Water, Air, & Soil Pollution
2	2020	Baloochi, H.; Aponte, D.; Barra, M. Soil stabilization using waste paper Fly ash: precautions for its correct use Applied Sciences 10, 8750 Date: 2020 Pages:1-15 doi: 10.3390/app10238750. ISSN: 2076-3417 Impact factor: 2.679 Quartile: Q2 73/160 (Category: Applied Physics)	UPC	WP3	Laboratory testing	Open Access	MDPI	https://doi.org/10.3390/app10238750	Applied Sciences 10.23 (2020): 8750.
3	2021	Karmen Fifer Bizjak, Barbara Likar and Stanislav Lenart (2021) Using Recycled Material from the Paper Industry as a Backfill Material for Retaining Walls near Railway	ZAG	WP4	Laboratory testing	Open Access	MDPI	https://doi.org/10.3390/su13020979	Sustainability Journal

#	PUBLIC ATION DATE	ARTICLES IN INDEXED JOURNALS	PARTNERS INVOLVED	WP	TOPICS	ACCESS RIGHT	REPOSITOR Y	DOI	JOURNAL TITLE
		Lines Sustainability 2021, 13(2), 979							
4	2021	Amaia Sopelana, Camille Auriault, Anurag Bansal, Karmen Fifer, Helena Paiva, Christian Maurice, Gunnar Westins, Javier Rios, Asier Oleaga and Antonio Cañas Innovative Circular Economy Models for European Pulp and Paper Industry: a reference framework for a resource recovery scenario. Sustainability	TECNALIA, LGI, ACCIONA, ZAG, AVEIRO, BOLIDEN, SP PROCESSUM, GAIKER, GREENIZE	WP3	Circular Business model innovation	Embargoed Access	MDPI	In progress	Sustainability Journal
5	2021	Fábio Simões, Javier Rios, Helena Paiva, Hamid Maljaee, Miguel Morais and Victor M. Ferreira Sustainability evaluation using a life cycle and circular economy approach in precast concrete with waste incorporation Sustainability	UAVR, GAIKER	WP5 , WP6	Circular case sustainability model	Open Access	MDPI	In progress	Sustainability Journal
6	2021	Fábio Simões, Javier Rios, Helena Paiva, Hamid Maljaee, Miguel Morais and Victor M. Ferreira Sustainability analysis in road bituminous pavements with wastes by a life cycle and circular economy	UAVR, GAIKER	WP5 , WP6	Circular case sustainability model	Open Access	MDPI	In progress	Sustainability Journal

#	PUBLIC ATION DATE	ARTICLES IN INDEXED JOURNALS	PARTNERS INVOLVED	WP	TOPICS	ACCESS RIGHT	REPOSITOR Y	DOI	JOURNAL TITLE
		perspective Sustainability							
7	2021	Fábio Simões, Amaia Sopelana, Helena Paiva, Hamid Maljaee, Miguel Morais and Victor M. Ferreira Circular business model analysis in the incorporation of a paper and pulp industrial waste in precast concrete manufacture Sustainability	UAVR, TECNALIA	WP3 , WP8	Circular Business model innovation	Open Access	MDPI	In progress	Sustainabili ty Journal
8	2021	Fábio Simões, Amaia Sopelana, Helena Paiva, Hamid Maljaee, Miguel Morais and Victor M. Ferreira Circular business model evaluatuin in the production of road pavements with bituminous mixtures containing industrial wastes Sustainability	UAVR, TECNALIA	WP3 , WP8	Circular Busniness model innovation	Open Access	MDPI	In progress	Sustainabili ty Journal
9	2021	Karmen Fifer Bizjak, Barbara Likar, Ana Mladenovič, Vesna Zalar Serjun Valorized deinking paper residue as fill material for geotechnical structures	ZAG	WP5	Field and laboratory testing	Open Access	SPRINGER	In progress	Scientific Reports

#	PUBLIC ATION DATE	ARTICLES IN INDEXED JOURNALS	PARTNERS INVOLVED	WP	TOPICS	ACCESS RIGHT	REPOSITOR Y	DOI	JOURNAL TITLE
10	2021	Karmen Fifer Bizjak, Barbara Likar, Stanislav Lenart Landslide stabilisation with a supporting structure composed of recycled backfill material	ZAG	WP5	Field and laboratory testing	Open Access	SPRINGER	In progress	Engineerin g geology

9.3 BOOKS / CHAPTERS

#	YEAR	BOOKS	PUBLISHER	ISBN	PARTNER INVOLVED	DOI	LINK TO THE CONGRESS RESPOSITORY
1	2020	"LIKAR, Barbara, VOVČKO, Laura. The use of paper industry side product in construction. V: BOGATAJ, Miloš (ur.), KRAVANJA, Zdravko (ur.), NOVAK-PINTARIČ, Zorka (ur.). 2nd International Conference on Technologies & Business Models for Circular Economy : conference proceedings. 1st ed. Maribor: University Press: Faculty of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering. 2020, pp 1-10, [COBISS.SI-ID 24287747]"	Maribor: University Press: Faculty of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering. 2020	978-961-286-353-1 (pdf)	ZAG	https://doi.org/10.18690/978-961-286-353-1	https://press.um.si/index.php/ump/catalog/view/472/570/801-1.
2	2019	β Paiva, H., Simões, F., Morais, M., & Ferreira, V. M. (2019). Pilot test involving pulp and paper industry wastes in road pavements. Wastes: Solutions, Treatments and Opportunities III; Vilarinho, C., Castro, F., Gonçalves, M., Fernando, AL, Eds, 20-26.	Vilarinho, C., Castro, F., Gonçalves, M., Fernando, AL, Eds	1000712419, 9781000712414	UA		

#	YEAR	BOOKS	PUBLISHER	ISBN	PARTNER INVOLVED	DOI	LINK TO THE CONGRESS RESPOSITORY
3	2021	<p>Aponte, D.; Baloochi, H.; Barra, M.; Martinez, A.; Miro, R.; Cepria, J.; Orejana, R. Chapter 22: Alternative secondary raw materials for road construction based on pulp and paper industry waste</p> <p>Waste and Byproducts in cement-based materials: Innovative sustainable materials for a circular economy, Eddited by De Brito, J.; Thomas, C.; Medina, C.; Agrela F., pages 635-657</p>	Woodhead Publishing (Elsevier)	<p>978-12-820895-3 online 978-0-12-820549-5 paperback</p>	UPC ACCION A	https://doi.org/10.1016/C2019-0-01771-2	

9.4 THESIS

#	YEAR	THESIS AWARDING UNIVERSITY	GRADE	CANDIDATE	TITLE	ISBN	REPOSITORY	REPOSITORY / DOI
1	2018	LTU - Luleå University of Technology	Master	Anna Virolainen	Evaluating the effective oxygen diffusion coefficient in blends of till and green liquor dregs (GLD) used as sealing layer in mine waste covers.		DIVA (LTU)	http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2:1270221

#	YEAR	THESIS AWARDING UNIVERSITY	GRADE	CANDIDATE	TITLE	ISBN	REPOSITORY	REPOSITORY / DOI
2	2018	LTU - Luleå University of Technology	Licenciatura	Susanne Nigeus	Green liquor dregs-amended fill to cover sulfidic mine waste.	ISBN: 978-91-7790-145-7 (electronic)	DIVA (LTU)	http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A1204180&dswid=8275
3	2021 (In progress)	UPC - Universidad Politècnica de Catalunya	PhD.	Hani Baloochi	Use of alternative materials in soil stabilization: Mechanical and durability aspects. Doctorate programme: Construction Engineering			
4	2021 (In progress)	UAVR - Aveiro University	PhD.	Fábio Simões	Circular economy approach to construction materials incorporating paper & pulp industry wastes. Doctoral programme: Civil Engineering			

9.5 CONFERENCE PAPERS and POSTERS

#	YEAR	CONFERENCE	CONFERENCE PAPERS and POSTERS	LINK TO PUBLICATION	OPEN ACCESS?	REPOSITORY / JOURNAL / PUBLISHER	PERMAMENT LINK / DOI	PARTNER
1	2022	BCRRA2022 - 11th International Conference on the Bearing Capacity of Roads , Railways and Airfields	Cepriá, J.J.; Orejana, R.; Miró, R.; Martínez, A.; Barra, M.; Aponte, D.; Baloochi, H. Waste Paper Ash as an Alternative Binder to Improve the Bearing Capacity of Road Subgrades Congress: BCRRA2022 – 11th International Conference on the Bearing Capacity of Roads, Railways and Airfields Venue: Trondheim Date: 28-30 June 2022 (postponed)					ACCIONA
2	2021	IMWA - VIRTUAL SYMPOSIUM 2021 ON MINES AND THE ENVIRONMENT	Christian Maurice, Ida Kronsell, Alaleh Ziagharib, Susanne Nigéus, Josef Mácsik, Gunnar Westin, Thomas Pabst. (2021). Amelioration of glacial till with waste from the pulp and paper industry for the construction of sealing layer. VIRTUAL SYMPOSIUM 2021 ON MINES AND THE ENVIRONMENT. June 14-16, 2021, Rouyn-Noranda, Quebec.					LTU

#	YEAR	CONFERENCE	CONFERENCE PAPERS and POSTERS	LINK TO PUBLICATION	OPEN ACCESS?	REPOSITORY / JOURNAL / PUBLISHER	PERMAMENT LINK / DOI	PARTNER
3	2020	E-UNSAT 2020	Ida Kronsell, Susanne Nigéus, Anna Virolainen, Yu Jia, Thomas Pabst and Christian Maurice (2020). Amelioration of permeable soil with green liquor dregs for the construction of sealing layers for mine waste storage facilities. E-UNSAT 2020. E3S Web of Conferences 195, 06006 (2020)	https://www.e3s-conferences.org/articles/e3sconf/pdf/2020/55/e3sconf_e-unsat2020_06006.pdf	YES (Green)	E3S WEB OF CONFERENCES	https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202019506006	LTU
4	2019	ERSCP2019: OpenConf Peer Review & Conference Management System (pp. 1-1). Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC). In Press.	Ríos-Davila, F. J., Barruetabeña-Oregui, L., Cañas Rojas, A., Orejana Gonzalez, R., Sopelana, A., Miró Recasens, J. R., & Martínez Reguero, A. H. (2019). paperChain: new market niches for the paper industry waste based on circular economy and sustainability approaches. In ERSCP2019: OpenConf Peer Review & Conference Management System (pp. 1-1). Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC). In Press.					GAIKER

#	YEAR	CONFERENCE	CONFERENCE PAPERS and POSTERS	LINK TO PUBLICATION	OPEN ACCESS?	REPOSITORY / JOURNAL / PUBLISHER	PERMANENT LINK / DOI	PARTNER
5	2019	DITP - Slovenian symposium of the paper industry	FIFER BIZJAK, Karmen, ŠEPETA VC, Justina, MLADENOV IČ, Ana, LIKAR, Barbara, LENART, Stanislav. The use of recycled materials from paper production in civil engineering : EU projekt Paperchain Between circular, bio and digital : book of abstracts, 23. Slovenian symposium of the paper industry in 46. international symposium of Association of Paper Engineers and Technicians of Slovenia (DITP), 20. - 21. november 2019, Postojna, Slove. Ljubljana: GZS ZPPPI: DITP. 2019, 53-54.	https://plus.si.co.biss.net/opac7/bib/2562663				ZAG, VIPAP
6	2019	26th World Road Congress Abu Dhabi 2019	PAPER Baloochi, H., Aponte Hernández, D. F., Barra Bizinotto, M., Martínez Reguero, A. H., Miró Recasens, J. R., Cepriá, J. J., ... & Oleaga, A. (2019). Alternative secondary raw materials for road construction based on pulp and paper industry reject: paperChain project. In 26th World Road Congress Abu Dhabi 2019: Connecting cultures, Enabling Economies (pp. 1-16). World Road Association (PIARC).	https://www.piarc.org/es/pedid-o-de-publicacion/32887-es-Materias%20primas%20secundarias%20para%20la%20construccion%20de%20carreteras%20basadas%20en%20rech	NO. Paid article	PIARC		UPC

#	YEAR	CONFERENCE	CONFERENCE PAPERS and POSTERS	LINK TO PUBLICATION	OPEN ACCESS?	REPOSITORY / JOURNAL / PUBLISHER	PERMANENT LINK / DOI	PARTNER
				azos%20de%20la%20industria%20papelera%20-%20El%20proyecto%20paperChain				
7	2019	26th World Road Congress Abu Dhabi 2019	<p>POSTER Baloochi, H., Aponte Hernández, D. F., Barra Bizinotto, M., Martínez Reguero, A. H., Miró Recasens, J. R., Cepriá, J. J., ... & Oleaga, A. (2019). Alternative secondary raw materials for road construction based on pulp and paper industry reject: paperChain project. In 26th World Road Congress Abu Dhabi 2019: Connecting cultures, Enabling Economies (pp. 1-16). World Road Association (PIARC).</p>		YES. (Green)	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5294190	UPC

#	YEAR	CONFERENCE	CONFERENCE PAPERS and POSTERS	LINK TO PUBLICATION	OPEN ACCESS?	REPOSITORY / JOURNAL / PUBLISHER	PERMANENT LINK / DOI	PARTNER
8	2018	11th ICARD IMWA WISA MWD 2018 Conference - INTERNATIONAL MINE WATER ASSOCIATION	Nigéus. S, Maurice. C (2018). Monitoring a field application of a Green Liquor Dregs-till mixture in a sealing layer on top of sulfidic mine waste. 11th ICARD IMWA WISA MWD 2018 Conference, Risk to Opportunity, s. 57-63, 2018.	http://ltu.diva-portal.org/smah/get/diva2:1268160/FULLTEXT01.pdf	YES	DIVA PORTAL (LTU)	http://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:ltu:diva-71890	LTU
9	2018	DITP - Slovenian symposium of the paper industry	DOLENEC, Sabina, LENART, Stanislav, TUŠAR, Marjan, FIFER BIZJAK, Karmen, DUCMAN, Vilma, FRANKOVIČ, Ana Potential use of paper sludge and paper sludge ash in construction sector Between circular, bio and digital : book of abstracts, 22. Slovenian symposium of the paper industry in 45. international symposium of Association of Paper Engineers and Technicians of Slovenia (DITP), 14. - 15. november 2019, BLED, Slove. Ljubljana: GZS ZPPPI: DITP. 2019, 53-54.	https://plus.si.co.biss.net/opac7/bib/2413159				ZAG, VIPAP
10	2017	13th International Mine Water Association Congress	POSTER Cepriá, J. J., Guedella, E., Maurice, C., & Westin, G. (2017) Paperchain Project: Establishing a New Circular Eco-	https://www.imwa.info/docs/imwa_2017/IMWA2017_Cepria_892.pdf	YES	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5278357	ACCIONA, LTU, Processum

#	YEAR	CONFERENCE	CONFERENCE PAPERS and POSTERS	LINK TO PUBLICATION	OPEN ACCESS?	REPOSITORY / JOURNAL / PUBLISHER	PERMAMENT LINK / DOI	PARTNER
		Mine Water and Circular Economy	onomy Model between the Mining Sector and the Pulp & Paper Industry to Prevent Acid Mine Drainage.					
11	2021	XXV International Conference of Forest, Pulp & Paper (Tecnicepa)	POSTER Nazaré S. Almeida, Susana Pereira, Pedro Branco, Luís Machado, Paula C. R. Pinto. Implementation of two circular economy demonstration cases in Portugal: Challenges and Learnings.					RAIZ (The Navigator Company)

9.6 DELIVERABLES

WP No	DELIVERABLE	Nature	Dissemination Level	DATASET NAME	DOI (Open Access via Zenodo)
WP2	D2.1	Report	Public	Baseline Report:PPI waste streams valorisation potential	10.5281/zenodo.5274774
WP2	D2.3	Report	Public	EU Raw material supply scenario	10.5281/zenodo.5275083
WP2	D2.4	Report	Public	Technological and non-technological barriers and constraints	10.5281/zenodo.5276903
WP3	D3.1	Report	Public	Comprehensive analysis of the existing and emerging approaches of circular economy models in pulp and paper industry	10.5281/zenodo.5270275
WP3	D3.2	Report	Public	Reference framework for the circular economy models	10.5281/zenodo.5275320
WP4	D4.3	Report	Public	Recycling analysis of the end-of life of developed products	10.5281/zenodo.5275378
WP5	D5.1	Demonstrator	Public	Implementation of Circular Case 5. Mining sector	10.5281/zenodo.5275438
WP5	D5.2	Demonstrator	Public	Implementation of Circular Case 1. Asphalt and concrete applications	10.5281/zenodo.5275469
WP5	D5.3	Demonstrator	Public	Implementation of Circular Case 2. Road applications	10.5281/zenodo.5275505

WP No	DELIVERABLE	Nature	Dissemination Level	DATASET NAME	DOI (Open Access via Zenodo)
WP5	D5.4	Demonstrator	Public	Implementation of Circular Case 3. Railway applications	10.5281/zenodo.5275539
WP5	D5.5	Demonstrator	Public	Implementation of Circular Case 4. Chemical industry	10.5281/zenodo.5275591
WP5	D5.6	Demonstrator	Public	Performance of Circular Case 1. Asphalt and concrete applications	10.5281/zenodo.5275677
WP5	D5.7	Demonstrator	Public	Performance of Circular Case 2. Road applications	10.5281/zenodo.5275803
WP5	D5.8	Demonstrator	Public	Performance of Circular Case 3. Railway applications	10.5281/zenodo.5275844
WP5	D5.9	Demonstrator	Public	Performance of Circular Case 4. Chemical industry	10.5281/zenodo.5275847
WP5	D5.10	Demonstrator	Public	Performance of Circular Case 5. Mining sector	10.5281/zenodo.5275849
WP5	D5.11	Report	Public	Integrated report on demonstration activities	10.5281/zenodo.5307921
WP6	D6.1	Report	Public	Sustainability improvements evaluation	10.5281/zenodo.5307977
WP6	D6.2	Report	Public	Circularity improvement evaluation: Results of the MCI of developed products	10.5281/zenodo.5308047
WP7	D7.3	Report	Public	Guidelines for the implementation of the Circular Economy models.	10.5281/zenodo.5308111

WP No	DELIVERABLE	Nature	Dissemination Level	DATASET NAME	DOI (Open Access via Zenodo)
WP9	D9.1	Report	Public	Communication and dissemination strategy and plan	10.5281/zenodo.5275888
WP9	D9.2	ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot	Public	Data Management Plan	10.5281/zenodo.5276073
WP9	D9.3	Websites, patents filing, etc.	Public	Communication and dissemination materials	10.5281/zenodo.5276129
WP9	D9.4	Report	Public	Report on Events: workshops, conferences, stands in exhibition fairs, trainings	10.5281/zenodo.5276223
WP9	D9.5	ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot	Public	Final data management plan	10.5281/zenodo.5308169

9.7 VIDEOS

DATASET - Video format mp4-	REPOSITORY	DOI URL
CC1 VIDEO ANIMATION	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5276511
CC1 VIDEO ANIMATION (Portuguese)	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5276635
CC2 VIDEO ANIMATION	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5276687
CC2 VIDEO ANIMATION (Spanish)	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.5307720
CC3 VIDEO ANIMATION	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5276791
CC4 VIDEO ANIMATION	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5276793
CC5 VIDEO ANIMATION	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5276797
GENERAL - VIDEO ANIMATION	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.5307799

9.8 LEAFLETS, TRIFOLD & ROLLUPS

DATASET: COMMUNICATION MATERIAL DESCRIPTION - pdf format -	REPOSITORY	DOI
CC1 LEAFLET	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5277979
CC2 LEAFLET	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5278101
CC3 LEAFLET	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5278173
CC4 LEAFLET	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5278207
CC5 LEAFLET	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5278279
TRIFOLD	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5278314
ROLLUP - CC1	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5278482
ROLLUP - CC2	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5278603
ROLLUP - CC3	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5278680
ROLLUP - CC4	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5278750
ROLLUP - CC5	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5278834
ROLLUP - Generic	ZENODO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5278891